

IMPROVING MODEL OF CORPORATE GOVERNANCE EFFICIENCY INDEX FOR UZBEK JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES

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Abstract

This article develops an index model aimed at further improving the system for assessing the effectiveness of corporate governance in joint-stock companies in Uzbekistan. An improved set of indicators has been proposed based on existing international standards - in particular, the principles of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), the recommendations of the World Bank and the International Finance Corporation. During the analysis, this model was practically tested using the example of several large joint-stock companies in Uzbekistan.

The research results showed that the proposed improved index model provides a qualitative assessment of corporate governance, increases investment attractiveness, and enhances transparency and responsibility in management. The index is also distinguished by the fact that it is developed based on criteria adapted to the conditions of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Corporate governance, Performance Index, Joint Stock Company, International Standards, OECD Principles, Conflict of Interest, Transparency, Investment Attractiveness, Uzbekistan's Experience, Internal Control.

Introduction

In a market economy, the corporate governance system is not only a tool for ensuring the effectiveness of joint-stock companies but also one of the important factors contributing to increasing investor confidence, the sustainable development of companies, and the development of the capital market. Especially in joint-stock companies, the formation of management principles in accordance with international standards increases the competitiveness of enterprises and plays an important role in their involvement in global economic integration.

In recent years, a number of measures have been taken in the Republic of Uzbekistan to reform the field of corporate governance. In particular, the "Strategy for Management and Reform of Enterprises with State Participation for 2021-2025", approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 166 dated March 29, 2021, defines the introduction of modern corporate governance mechanisms in joint-stock companies with state participation, increasing their openness and effectiveness as the main priority.

At the same time, the limited possibilities of systematically measuring the effectiveness of corporate governance in existing assessment mechanisms, the uniformity of existing approaches, and their inconsistency with international criteria hinder the comprehensive assessment of enterprise activities. This situation hinders the full achievement of the goals stipulated in state corporate governance development strategies.

International experience shows that the implementation of advanced corporate governance principles increases the stability and investment attractiveness of companies. For example, in 2023, the updated G20/OECD Corporate Governance Principles included new and updated guidelines on shareholder rights, information transparency, responsibilities of the board of directors, and, for the first time, sustainability and resilience. These principles aim to provide companies

with financing from capital markets, protect investors, and help companies, as well as our economy, become more stable.

Furthermore, the Corporate Governance Methodology, developed by the International Finance Corporation, provides a general approach to evaluating and improving the management practices of companies. This methodology provides a general approach to evaluating and improving company management practices, including environmental and social risk management, the effectiveness of the board of directors, and stakeholder relations.

Considering this situation, there is a need to improve and implement the Corporate Governance Performance Index (CGPI), which has been improved based on international experience and adapted to the conditions of Uzbekistan. The proposed index model expands the possibilities of assessing the quality of management in joint-stock companies based on specific criteria, identifying existing problems, and making strategic decisions to eliminate them.

Analysis of literature on the topic

In recent years, extensive research has been conducted to improve the corporate governance system, assess its effectiveness, and adapt it to international standards. By analyzing the literature in this area, it is possible to identify existing scientific views, approaches, and gaps.

Corporate governance assessment systems are widely used internationally. In particular, the "G20/OECD Corporate Governance Principles", developed by the OECD, are used as the main methodological tool in many countries of the world. These principles are aimed at strengthening the trust of institutional investors, improving the activities of the board of directors, and eliminating conflicts of interest. The OECD principles, newly published in 2023, serve as a universal criterion for assessing management standards at the international level.

The Corporate Governance Rating, developed by the International Finance Corporation (International Finance Corporation) in 2021, has been implemented in such countries as Mexico, Indonesia, the Philippines, Georgia, and has yielded effective results in assessing management effectiveness. This model assesses based on 5 areas: shareholder rights, management bodies' activities, information openness, control system, and conflict of interest.

The World Bank also assesses the management system of companies, the legal environment, and investor protection indicators in its Doing Business and Governance Indicator reports. According to 2020 data, the investor protection index in Uzbekistan was relatively low on a 5.0/10 score system, which confirms the relevance of the reforms.

In the "Corruption Perception Index" presented by Transparency International in 2023, Uzbekistan ranked 126th out of 180 countries. This indicates that the issues of transparency and accountability remain relevant.

A number of studies and methodologies for assessing the effectiveness of corporate governance have been developed at the international level. In particular, in his work, Clarke substantiated the theory of stakeholders in corporate governance and showed that effectiveness should be assessed not only through financial results, but also through social and environmental responsibility. Aguilera and Cuervo-Cazurra, emphasizing that management effectiveness is directly related to the national institutional environment, substantiate the importance of the country's context in the selection of indicators.

Mallin analyzed the relationship between corporate governance effectiveness and indices (CG Index, ESG Index). In his research, the influence of international ratings and indices on investment attractiveness is deeply covered.

Uzbek scientists have carried out a number of important scientific works on corporate governance. In particular, E. Urinboev noted that increasing the transparency and quality of financial reporting in the activities of joint-stock companies in Uzbekistan is an important factor in the effectiveness of corporate governance.

A. Kurbanov, in his research, based on statistical analysis, substantiated the relationship between the independence of the board of directors and the effectiveness of the activities of executive bodies.

T. Egamberdiyev paid special attention to the issues of the internal audit system and conflict of interest management in assessing the effectiveness of corporate governance.

In his monograph, R. Makhmudov examines the institutional foundations of corporate governance in Uzbekistan, including the role of the supervisory board in joint-stock companies with state participation.

Although these works are of great importance, they do not sufficiently develop a methodology for indexing effectiveness or a comprehensive evaluation model.

Research methodology

The theoretical basis of the research is international scientific developments in the field of corporate

governance, in particular, standards and methodological guidelines developed by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, the World Bank, and the International Finance Corporation. Also, scientific views on assessing the effectiveness of corporate governance, research by foreign and domestic scientists, assessment systems, corporate governance indicators, ESG ratings determine the theoretical basis of the research.

The research methodology is based on a systematic approach, comprehensive analysis, multi-criteria assessment methods, statistical analysis, indexation, and modeling methods.

The study analyzed the structural elements of the corporate governance system in interconnection: the board of directors, shareholder rights, transparency, conflict of interest, and internal control systems.

The main goal of this study is to develop an improved index model that allows for a systematic assessment of the effectiveness of corporate governance in the activities of joint-stock companies in Uzbekistan, based on international experience and local conditions.

The research objectives are to study international systems for assessing the effectiveness of corporate governance, analyze the specific aspects of corporate governance in domestic practice, improve the system of criteria and indicators for the formation of an index model, and develop scientific conclusions and practical recommendations.

Analysis and results

Assessment of the effectiveness of corporate governance today plays an important role in increasing the stability, investment attractiveness, and transparency of joint-stock companies. In accordance with the strategy for reforming enterprises with state participation in our country, the task of improving the corporate governance system based on international standards has been set. Therefore, there is a need for a deep analysis of the existing system and the creation of a modern assessment mechanism.

Analysis shows that, although many joint-stock companies in Uzbekistan have corporate governance mechanisms, there is no single set of indicators that systematically assess their effectiveness. According to the 2023 monitoring, only 48% of joint-stock companies fully implemented the most important principles of corporate governance - such elements as the participation of independent directors, conflict of interest management, and information transparency. According to calculations by the World Bank and the International Finance Corporation, the developed level of corporate governance directly affects the financial performance of companies: ROE (share capital return) increases by an average of 12-15 percent[1].

Taking these circumstances into account, the study considered it expedient to develop a model of the corporate governance efficiency index, adapted to the conditions of Uzbekistan. The model was developed on the basis of international experience, in particular, recommendations of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, the International Finance Corporation, the World Bank, and is based on a quantitative (point) assessment of the state of the company's

corporate governance system according to 6 main criteria.

The index model consisted of the following main areas:

1. The independence of the board of directors is a structural factor that directly affects the number of independent members on the board, their real influence, political neutrality, company strategy, and control.

2. Protection of shareholder rights - Ensuring voting rights, dividend policy, guarantees of property interests, equal rights of majority and minority shareholders, and voting mechanisms.

3. Disclosure and transparency of information - Public disclosure of annual reports, financial results, decisions, disclosure of financial and corporate data, the level of accountability.

4. Internal control and audit system - a tool that ensures independent audit, the presence of risk assessment and monitoring mechanisms, independent control over the legality and effectiveness of the company's activities.

5. Conflict of interest regulation mechanism - Internal policies, codes, activities of ethics committees, prevention of corruption and maintaining balance between stakeholders.

6. Sustainability and resilience - ESG, Sustainable Development Strategy Availability, Risk Management and Crisis Resilience, Social Responsibility, Corporate Sustainability Reports, Energy Efficiency and Green Initiatives.

When assessing the corporate governance system, it is possible to assess the commitment of companies to

long-term development by including the "Stability and Strength" indicator in the areas of the existing indicator. This indicator assesses the long-term sustainable development of corporate governance, the economic, environmental, and social stability of the company. The criterion takes into account the following structural elements:

- Compliance with ESG (Environmental, Social, Governance) principles - the company's practices that minimize environmental impact, ensure social stability, and guarantee the integrity of management processes.

- Availability of a sustainable development strategy - strategies that meet the UN Sustainable Development Goals, taking into account the social and environmental impacts of the company's activities.

- Risk management and crisis resilience - the presence of stable systems against economic, financial, environmental, and other operational threats.

- Social responsibility and participation - the level of responsible and transparent cooperation of the company with local communities, workers, and other stakeholders.

- Corporate sustainability reports - publication of sustainability reports in accordance with GRI (Global Reporting Initiative) or other international standards.

- Energy efficiency and green initiatives - initiatives related to the use of renewable energy sources, waste reduction, and environmental safety.

When assessing the stability and strength criterion, it is necessary to pay attention to the following main aspects.

Main aspects to consider when assessing the stability and strength criterion

No.	Stability and strength criterion	Key points to consider
1.	Strategic integration	Are sustainability and social responsibility considered an integral part of the company's corporate strategy?
		Are ESG principles (Environmental, Social, Governance) reflected in the company's strategic plans?
2.	Environmental responsibility	What measures is the company taking to avoid harming the environment?
		The level of use of renewable energy, the availability of a waste processing system.
		Energy efficiency, indicators of rational use of water and air resources.
3.	Social responsibility	Compliance with standards for the protection of workers' rights, health and safety.
		Connections with local communities, participation in charitable and social projects.
		Gender equality, the state of creating conditions for persons with disabilities.
4.	External evaluation and reporting	Does the company provide regular reporting based on GRI, SASB, TCFD, or other international sustainability reporting standards?
		Are the main ESG indicators fully and transparently presented in the reports?
		Have ESG indicators been assessed by independent external auditors or rating agencies?
5.	Risk Management and Sustainability Adaptation	Has a sustainability plan been developed for environmental, social, and economic threats?
		What measures does the company take in the event of unexpected crises (economic, climatic, pandemic, etc.)?
		Level of readiness for digital transformation and technological development.
6.	Relation to corporate governance	Are sustainability principles included on the agenda of the board of directors or governing bodies?
		Is there an internal structure (for example, an ESG committee) responsible for issues related to ESG?
		Are there sustainability commitments in the company's charter or policy documents?

International investors make decisions based on ESG indicators, which increases investor confidence. This is a relevant criterion for Uzbekistan's integration into the global financial system.

Each criterion is assessed from 0 to 100 points, the maximum score is 100 points. The overall index is the average score for 6 criteria. In the study, the following formula was used to calculate the Corporate Governance Performance Index (CGPI):

$$KBSI_i = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n S_{ij}$$

Here S_{ij} - i - the company's score according to the j -criterion, and n - the number of evaluation criteria (6: independence of the board of directors, shareholder rights, information openness, internal audit system, conflict of interest regulation mechanism, stability and strength). This approach allows for an objective assessment of the management of the joint-stock company, identification of weaknesses, and planning measures for further improvement.

The results are displayed on a 100-point scale, and the company is ranked:

85-100 points - High Performance

70-84 points - Average effectiveness

55-69 points - Satisfactory, but needs development

Up to 54 points - Weak corporate governance

Based on this model, joint-stock companies identify weaknesses in their management system, investors and state organizations give an accurate assessment of the management of a joint-stock company. Also, based on comparative analysis, it is possible to conduct analyses by industry or region or develop roadmaps for joint-stock companies to improve corporate governance.

Within the framework of the study, indices were calculated based on the financial and corporate reports of 30 large joint-stock companies for the period 2020-2023.

Table 2.

Corporate Governance Performance Index of Joint-Stock Companies

No	Name of the joint-stock company	Independence of the Board of Directors	Protection of shareholders' rights	Disclosure and transparency of information	Internal control and audit system	Conflict of interest settlement mechanism	Stability and strength	General index
1.	JSC "O'zbekiston temir yo'llari"	88.	78.	64.	92.	57.	70.	74.8
2.	"O'zbekneftgaz" JSC	70.	88.	68.	72.	60.	65.	70.5
3.	JSC "O'zavtosanoat"	60.	73.	85.	89.	73.	75.	75.8
4.	"O'zmetkombinat" JSC	52.	71.	51.	73.	93.	60.	66.6
5.	JSC "Olmaliq KMK"	79.	87.	51.	70.	82.	72.	73.5
6.	"Navoiy KMK" JSC	61.	71.	93.	74.	98.	74.	78.5
7.	JSC "O'ztransgaz"	76.	91.	77	65.	64.	68.	73.5
8.	JSC "O'zbekko'mir"	96.	100.	93.	52.	86.	69.	82.6
9.	Uzbektelecom JSC	100.	56.	70.	58.	88.	76.	74.6
10.	JSCB "O'zsanoat qurilishbank"	67.	53.	74.	63.	99.	67.	70.5
11.	JSC "O'zmilliybank"	58.	75.	51.	69.	77	62.	65.3.
12.	"Agrobank" JSCB	96.	56.	93.	57.	96.	73.	78.5
13.	"Qishloqqurilishbank" JSCB	84.	63.	66.	85.	99.	71.	78.0
14.	"Asakabank" JSCB	89.	53.	51.	55.	91.	64.	67.1
15.	"Mikrokreditbank" JSCB	53.	78.	67.	75.	93.	70.	72.6
16.	"Turonbank" JSCB	83.	59.	85.	63.	80.	66.	72.6
17.	"Aloqabank" JSCB	97.	64.	57.	63.	72.	72.	70.8
18.	JSC "Navoiyazot"	89.	70.	65.	94.	67.	75.	76.6
19.	JSC "O'zbekiston pochtasi"	96.	73.	75.	74.	94.	74.	81.0
20.	JSC "Hududgazta'minot"	90.	78.	64.	94.	50.	65.	73.5
21.	JSC "Issiqlik elektr stansiyalari"	74.	56.	58.	73.	50.	68.	63.1.
22.	JSC "Thermal Power Plants"	93.	57.	73.	60.	100.	70.	75.5
23.	"O'zbekiston milliy elektr tarmoqlari" JSC	66.	57.	84.	84.	82.	71.	74.0
24.	"O'zbekgidroenergo" JSC	54.	91.	88.	90.	77	67.	77.8
25.	"Navoiyuran" State Enterprise	56.	58.	57.	61.	83.	64.	63.1.
26.	Uzbekistan Airports JSC	82.	97.	72.	73.	86.	78.	81.3
27.	Uzbekistan Airways JSC	84.	93.	89.	71.	76.	76.	81.5
28.	"Toshshahartransxizmat" JSC	84.	50.	84.	86.	96.	69.	78.1
29.	UzGasTrade JSC	63.	52.	50.	54.	75.	62.	59.3
30.	JSC "Uzparkurilish"	63.	88.	76.	58.	64.	68.	69.5

The results of the analysis showed that JSC "O'zbekko'mir", JSC "O'zbekiston pochtasi", JSC "Uzbekistan Airports", JSC "Uzbekistan Airways", JSC "Navoi KMK", JSCB "Agrobank", JSCB "Qishloqqurilishbank", JSC "Toshshahartransxizmat", JSC "Navoiyazot", JSC "Uzbekgidroenergo" are joint-stock companies with the highest total index indicators. These joint-stock companies have a stable approach in all areas of corporate governance, especially high scores on such criteria as shareholder rights, information transparency, and conflict of interest regulation.

The majority of enterprises (about 60%) have an index score in the range of 70-80 points, which indicates that they have a partially systematic approach to corporate governance.

Joint-stock companies such as JSC "O'zmilliybank", JSC "Hududiy elektr tarmoqlari", JSC "UzGasTrade" have a relatively low index, and there is a weak approach, especially in terms of the independence of the board of directors and the criteria of information

openness. Weaknesses are also observed in the internal control and conflict of interest regulation system at these enterprises.

In general, in most joint-stock companies, the results on the independence of the board of directors (around 60-70 points), openness of information, and stability and resilience (around 65-75 points) are relatively low. This indicates the weakness of mechanisms for transparency, external monitoring, and independent decision-making in joint-stock companies.

These results confirm the practical usefulness of the proposed index model. This approach can be used not only for assessing the effectiveness of company management, but also for developing roadmaps for their development.

Conclusion

Assessment and improvement of the corporate governance system of joint-stock companies in Uzbekistan is one of the urgent issues. The Corporate Governance Performance Index (KBPI) model, developed

based on the research results, allows for the assessment of the management activities of companies directly based on 5 criteria: independence of the board of directors, shareholder rights, information openness, internal control and audit system, and conflict of interest management mechanism.

Through the practical application of the index, the level of corporate governance of 30 large joint-stock companies was analyzed. The results of the analysis show that there are significant differences in the quality of management between companies, some of which have a high index, while others have serious shortcomings in this area. This confirms the practical significance of the proposed model and its use as an assessment tool. The proposed index model led to the following main conclusions:

Implementation of the corporate governance efficiency index model as a national standard: Adoption of this index as a single criterion for assessing the activities of joint-stock companies and establishing the practice of annual monitoring.

Strengthening legal requirements to increase information openness: According to the index results, information openness is one of the lowest indicators, and attention should be paid to this area.

Strengthening the institution of independent directors: Developing legal and organizational mechanisms to increase the proportion of independent members on the Board of Directors.

Standardization of the conflict of interest regulation system: Implementation of a unified methodology and internal regulations for this mechanism in companies.

Creation of a rating and audit system for companies based on the results of the index: This will allow providing investors with reliable information and improving the culture of corporate governance.

Development of special roadmaps for companies with state participation: For joint-stock companies with low indicators, it is necessary to form a program of systemic reforms based on the results of CGPI.

Through the Corporate Governance Performance Index, it will be possible to regularly assess the level of corporate governance not only of large, but also of medium and small joint-stock companies, which will contribute to the formation of a stable and competitive corporate governance environment at the national level. It also serves to increase the transparency of joint-stock companies' activities, investment attractiveness, and management quality.

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